

DETERMINING THE SPATIAL DISTRIBUTION OF CARBON FIBRES IN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

An economical large area, high resolution image analyser is being developed primarily to study fibre orientations in injection moulded thermoplastics by reflection microscopy. Thousands of circular and elliptical images are decoded efficiently using a transputer network and parallel processing techniques. Software has been written to automatically demerge touching images at high packing fractions. Instrumental limitations are discussed and it is shown that, by careful choice of serial sectioning, orientation distributions may be computed with errors of a few degrees. By deducing the absolute fibre positions on different serial sections and identifying images of the same fibre by pattern matching between sections, an accurate 3D spatial distribution of fibres may be derived.

KEYWORDS: Microscopy; Short fibre composites; Morphology; Three dimensional.

1. INTRODUCTION

For the past few years, colleagues in the Polymer Group at the University of Leeds have been working on the properties of carbon fibres (mean length = $120\mu\text{m}$ and diameter = $7\mu\text{m}$) in polyether ether ketone (PEEK) and more recently on glass fibres in polyoxymethylene (POM). In order to model the movement of fibres in the manufacturing process and to predict the physical properties of these composite materials, it is essential to know the fibre lengths and the 3D fibre orientation distribution, (1), (2) and (3). The distribution of fibre lengths could be determined by pyrolytic decomposition of the sample, (4) and a number of techniques have been developed to determine the spatial distribution of fibres, eg (5), (6) and (7). One of the earliest techniques was reflection microscopy of polished

surfaces.

The cylindrical fibres form circular or elliptical images on the polished surface. The measurement of the elliptical parameters of each image may be used to deduce orientation distributions in θ_i and φ_i . However, in order to completely characterise a number $i = 1$ to N short, rod-like carbon fibres in a polymer composite, we would need to specify a parameter set $(\underline{r}_i, l_i, d_i, \theta_i, \varphi_i)$ where $\underline{r}_i = x_i\hat{i} + y_i\hat{j} + z_i\hat{k}$ is taken from a convenient origin to the centre coordinates of, say, the base of the fibre: l_i is the length of the i^{th} fibre: d_i is the diameter of the i^{th} fibre: θ_i is the angle that the fibre makes to the vertical and φ_i is the angle that the fibre makes to the y -axis in the plane of a serial section taken through the material as shown in Figure 1. We have set ourselves the task of deriving this parameter set for each of the thousands of fibres contained within a typical 2mm x 2mm area of a composite sample.

FIGURE 1. Classification of a Fibre

There are a number of research groups who have used commercial image processing systems for deducing average values of the θ_i and φ_i distributions from a serial section eg (4), (6) and (8). All of these groups have sought an efficient computerised method to illustrate the orientation averages at different locations in a large cross-section area sample. Each group has used the 'moments' technique to deduce the elliptical parameters of the images (9) and (10). Its main attraction is that it is a 'single pass' technique. The mathematical relationships between the first and second moments and the elliptical parameters are shown overpage. The summation is over all pixels within a fibre image and w_i is a weighting factor which in our case is unity (but may be set to pixel intensity in certain applications).

$$M_{xx} = \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})^2 w_i / \sum_i w_i = \sum_i x_i^2 w_i / \sum_i w_i - \bar{x}^2 \quad (1)$$

$$M_{yy} = \sum_i (y_i - \bar{y})^2 w_i / \sum_i w_i = \sum_i y_i^2 w_i / \sum_i w_i - \bar{y}^2 \quad (2)$$

$$M_{xy} = \sum_i (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y}) w_i / \sum_i w_i = \sum_i x_i y_i w_i / \sum_i w_i - \bar{x} \bar{y} \quad (3)$$

The centroids of the image are given by \bar{x} and \bar{y} , the semimajor axis is 'a' and the semiminor axis is 'b'. Note, there is an inherent 180° ambiguity in φ .

$$M_x = \sum_i x_i w_i / \sum_i w_i = \bar{x} \quad (4)$$

$$M_y = \sum_i y_i w_i / \sum_i w_i = \bar{y} \quad (5)$$

$$\varphi = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} [2M_{xy} / (M_{xx} - M_{yy})] \quad (6)$$

$$\theta = \cos^{-1} \left[\frac{b}{a} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$a = \sqrt{2(M_{xx} + M_{yy}) + 2[(M_{xx} - M_{yy})^2 + 4M_{xy}^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (8)$$

$$b = \sqrt{2(M_{xx} + M_{yy}) - 2[(M_{xx} - M_{yy})^2 + 4M_{xy}^2]^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (9)$$

2. SYSTEM OVERVIEW

For the past two years, a transputer based system has been developed which is essentially a large area, high resolution 2D image analyser (11). Figure 2 shows the T800 transputers and their interconnections via high speed data channels. The 'frame grabber' transputer is on a Quintek board which captures a 512 by 512 image to 8 bit precision from a Sony square-pixel CCD video camera. The frame grabber is linked to three short 'pipelines' which decode three equal areas of the screen in parallel. After thresholding, the single-pass 'moments' algorithm is used to compute the centre coordinates and the elliptical parameters of each image. The 'merger' at the end of the pipes combines incomplete images at the edges of each field of view. The 'control' transputer supervises operations, interfaces with a Prior Systems X-Y translation stage and autofocus unit on an Olympus BH2 microscope and also archives data onto hard disk. The transputer development system is on a Tandon microcomputer and all software is written in OCCAM. The success of this measurement technique depends upon the quality of the prepared sample. A Malvern Instruments Multipol 2 precision polishing machine is now used. An initial lapping stage using 8 μ m diamond abrasive on a cast iron lapping plate renders the specimen flat

FIGURE 2. The Basic Image Analyser

and removes any damage induced by cutting. After lapping, the cast iron plate is exchanged for a stainless steel polishing plate onto which a rigid cloth is mounted. A diamond abrasive (1 to $3\mu\text{m}$) is used to obtain the necessary finish for final examination. A short duration polish (20 to 30 minutes) enables a 4 or $5\mu\text{m}$ layer to be removed at a time.

3. POSITIONAL ACCURACY

The orientation of fibres within a 2mm by 2mm area is computed by combining image data from a large number of video frames. Many fibre images are to be found at the edge of a frame. Hence it is necessary to define the absolute positions of these partial images in order to reconstruct the complete image after a raster scan in X and Y. Although the reproducibility of repositioning is within ± 1 pixel, there is a lead screw cyclic variability when attempting to position the X-Y stage. The variation in the absolute Y positioning from one scan to another when this lead screw variability has been removed is shown in Figure 3. The absolute movement was determined by following an image from the top third of one frame to the bottom third of the next frame (when a fixed number of pulses was sent to the Y axis stepper motor).

FIGURE 3. Residual Positioning Errors

The average diameter of a circular image at our current magnification is 40 pixels ie twice the semiminor axis length. Therefore the residual positioning uncertainty of within ± 2 pixels gives good registration of images over the scanned area, without the need for expensive, absolute positioning sensors in X and Y.

4. FUNDAMENTAL PROBLEMS

Image decoding by the 'moments technique' assumes that the images will be perfectly elliptical in shape, but this is never the case in practice. There are a number of effects to consider.

- (a) Non elliptical images are produced by sectioning through the end of short fibre composites (4).
- (b) Surface preparation may yield ragged edge images.
- (c) Merging of two or more images in high packing fraction composites yields non-elliptical shapes.
- (d) The fibres are not perfectly cylindrical. As shown in Figure 4, some carbon fibres can exhibit a regular ribbing along the fibre.

FIGURE 4. SEM of a Carbon Fibre (scale in μm)

Also, fibres whose axes are perpendicular to the measurement plane have near circular images. The deviations from circularity depend upon the system magnification and digitisation of each pixel.

5. θ DISTRIBUTION ERRORS

All of these effects combine to give very poor performance in deducing the ' θ distribution' when serial sections are taken perpendicular to the main fibre axis direction of an oriented composite.

The situation may be improved by taking a number of serial sections and by pattern matching, correlate the images on different sections due to a particular fibre. The first results of such a pattern matching process yielded Figure 5 where the standard deviations of four independent samples of a fibre's image indicated the errors associated with the θ distributions.

In Figure 5 it can be seen that measurement errors in θ reduce dramatically for $\theta > 30^\circ$. Therefore, a better estimate of the true θ distribution may be derived by cutting the sample at 45° to the main fibre axis direction, and transforming mathematically the θ (and φ) to the 90° plane. The improvement is seen in Figure 6. The 90° section data give a totally false impression of θ orientations.

FIGURE 5. Typical Digitisation and Sample Preparation Errors

FIGURE 6. Results for a Highly Oriented Sample

6. ϕ DISTRIBUTION ERRORS

In order to deduce the ϕ errors, a number of serial sections were taken and, once again, by pattern matching, it was possible to make four independent samples of each fibre's orientation angle ϕ in the measurement plane.

The results are shown below in Figure 7. The standard deviation in angle ϕ is plotted against the mean, out of plane angle $\bar{\theta}$ for both the multiple serial sections and, for comparison, the errors due to digitisation of the same serial section.

FIGURE 7. Typical Digitisation and Sample Preparation Errors

Great care must be taken to deduce the correct 'aspect error ratio' for the image analysis system. If the ratio is in error by a few percent, the apparent ϕ distribution differs considerably from the true distribution for fibres with small θ values.

A technique has been developed, using the thousands of fibre images on a typical sample to deduce the 'aspect error ratio' to high precision. A ϕ distribution is derived for one sample orientation and, from this distribution, a ϕ distribution for a 90° sample rotation is predicted. Then the sample is rotated by 90° and an actual ϕ distribution is derived. The sum of the absolute differences between actual and predicted

distributions is computed for different aspect error ratios. A clear minimum is seen in this sum at an aspect error ratio of 1.135 (± 0.005) for our image analyser system.

FIGURE 8. Orientation of the Fibres in 913/DISCO

Preliminary measurements on a well-aligned (mean fibre length 3mm) composite (913/DISCO) have yielded interesting results. The composite consists of layers of carbon fibres in an epoxy resin matrix which have been compression moulded. A schematic diagram of the fibres in the sample and the definition of the φ orientation angle is shown in Figure 8. Data on this composite produced the θ distributions shown in Figure 6. Also the φ distribution, whether derived from a 90° cut to the main fibre direction or transformed from a 45° cut, shows a definite anisotropy. The φ distribution is shown in Figure 9. The interpretation of the anisotropy is that the fibres have more freedom of movement in the plane of the fibre layers rather than perpendicular to the layers. This anisotropy in φ agrees well with an observed anisotropy in the elastic modulus value derived from directional ultrasonic measurements.

FIGURE 9. Orientational Anisotropy in a Compression Moulded Composite

7. CONCLUSION

The image analyser is generating high quality 2D fibre orientation information on a range of short fibre and continuous fibre composites.

By taking multiple serial sections and pattern matching, the instrumental errors in θ and φ have been identified. The analyser is undergoing continuous development with a view to deducing the true 3D spatial distribution of fibres and fibre length distribution of short fibre composites.

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